

Unveiling the Clinicopathological Spectrum of Neuroendocrine Neoplasms in a Tertiary Care Setting

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Abstract:

Introduction: Neuroendocrine neoplasms are a heterogeneous group of malignancies showing various non-specific clinical symptoms, different morphological features, molecular involvement which makes it an important differential for all rapidly growing malignancies in our body since it has got a greater propensity to metastasize. The clinical symptoms depend on both the “neuro” and “endocrine” properties. Histopathologically, they form broader two groups of well differentiated and poorly differentiated neuroendocrine carcinomas and hence needs accurate grading depending on mitosis and Ki 67 counts. Hormonal and non-hormonal biomarkers like serum serotonin, urine 5-HIAA, gastrin and VIP are of equal relevance as well as histology. IHC markers for neuroendocrine neoplasms include synaptophysin, chromogranin, CD56 among others. Herein, we report all the neuroendocrine neoplasms detected in our setting for a period of 12 months and discuss extensively on the same.

Materials and Methods: This is a retrospective cross sectional study carried out in the histopathology section of Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and hospital, Cuttack. The total duration of the study was 12 months spanning from June 2023-June 2024. All the histopathological confirmed cases of neuroendocrine neoplasms based on recent 5th edition of WHO classification of endocrine and neuroendocrine tumors was analysed. Clinical data (age, sex, anatomical site) and histopathology along with IHC were studied.

Results: We found a total of 12 patients diagnosed with neuroendocrine neoplasms involving various organs of the body. The mean age of patients was 51.83 years with age varying from 7yrs to 80 yrs. Majority were females with male to female ratio being 7:5. Majority of cases in our setting had involved adrenal glands with three cases diagnosed as pheochromocytoma followed by carotid body tumor (paraganglioma) and medullary carcinoma of thyroid, each with 2 cases respectively and rest all the organs presented with one case each i.e. pituitary, gastric, duodenal, rectum and appendix.

Conclusion: In our cohort, the preponderance of pheochromocytomas was more followed by medullary carcinoma of thyroid and paraganglioma, with a notable female predominance. The diagnosis of neuroendocrine tumours necessitates meticulous radiological examination including USG, CT and MRI. Histopathology along with immunohistochemistry is imperative for arriving at a final diagnosis, accurate grading, and the formulation of an optimal management for the patient.

Keywords: Neuroendocrine Tumor, Paraganglioma, Pheochromocytoma, Synaptophysin, Chromogranin.

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Introduction

Neuroendocrine neoplasms are very rare when compared to other neoplasms in the body constituting 0.5% of all malignancies. The incidence rates are approximately 2/100,000 every year in developed countries, predominantly affecting females under the age of 50 years.1 Gastrointestinal tract and pancreas (70%) followed by bronchopulmonary system (20-30%) are the most common sites to be affected.

However, they can affect any part of the body extending from head and neck, thymus, breast, lungs, urogenital tract to even skin. [2] We aim to describe the relative frequencies, age and gender distribution, anatomical site of presentation of the various neuroendocrine neoplasms that presented to our centre for duration of 12 months. Our study also highlights the importance of histomorphological spectrum of

different neuroendocrine neoplasms and the importance of carrying out supportive methods like immunohistochemistry in the final confirmation of diagnosis.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College and Hospital, Cuttack during a period of – 12 months (from June 2023 to June 2024).

Complete history, clinical details and preoperative investigation findings wherever necessary of all cases were collected and analysed. The biopsy samples received were fixed in 10% buffered neutral formalin overnight. Paraffin embedded blocks were made, following which thin sections of 4-6 μ were

cut using microtome and tissue was stained by haematoxylin and eosin to be examined under microscope for histopathological examination. The neuroendocrine neoplasms were classified according to the latest WHO 2022 classification of endocrine tumours.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional ethics committee of our institution. The radiological investigations were also collected for final comparison and analysed from case records of department of radiology.

Grading was done based on WHO 2022 classification of endocrine and neuroendocrine tumors wherever necessary.

Results

Table 1: Clinicopathological Characteristics of Neuroendocrine Neoplasms

Case No.	Age	Gender	Clinical diagnoses	Gross findings (cut section)	Immunohistochemistry	Final diagnosis
1.	7 yr	Female	Space occupying lesion	Multiple greyish white tissue structures measuring 3x2x1.5cm	Synaptophysin and chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells	Pituitary Neuroectodermal Tumor
2.	50 yr	Female	Rectal polyp	Firm, homogenous nodule measuring 1cm	Synaptophysin and chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells but ck7 and ck20 negative in tumor cells.	Rectal Carcinoids
3.	72 yr	Male	?Pheochromocytoma	Adrenal gland measuring 6x5x2.5cm, cut section shows solid greyish white homogenous areas	Synaptophysin and chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells	Left Adrenal Pheochromocytoma
4.	80 yr	Male	?GIST ?NET	Multiple bits of greyish brown tissue measuring 4x3x1.5cm	Synaptophysin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells	Gastric Neuroendocrine Tumor, Grade 2
5.	67 yr	Female	? Thyroid swelling	Irregular bits of greyish white tissue measuring 5.5x5x3.5cm. Cut section shows gritty sensation, whitish brown solid homogenous areas, calcified areas seen	Synaptophysin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells	Medullary Thyroid Carcinoma
6.	60 yr	Male	?Neurofibroma ?Meningioma	Greyish brown globular tissue measuring 2.2x1.2x0.8cm	Synaptophysin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells	Paraganglioma
7.	56 yr	Female	? Adrenocortical carcinoma ?Atypical adenoma	Globular capsulated tissue measuring 6x5.5x3.8cm, weight = 77gms. Growth arising from medulla measuring 3x2cm	Synaptophysin and chromogranin, S100 shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells PASS <4	Pheochromocytoma

8.	48 yr	Female	?Pheochromocytoma	Adrenal gland with fibrofatty tissue measuring 7x5x3.5cm, cut section shows variegated areas, cyst containing hemorrhagic fluid	Synaptophysin, chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells	Pheochromocytoma
9.	25 yr	Female	? Carotid body tumor	Greyish brown flap like tissue structure measuring 6.5x4x2cm. Cut section showed solid, white, homogenous areas with a focus of brown area	-	Paraganglioma
10.	65 yr	Male	Acute appendicitis	Appendix with mesoappendix measuring 5x2x1cm	Chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells. Ki67 < 2%	Neuroendocrine Tumor Of Appendix (Grade 1)
11.	40 yr	Female	Duodenal polyp	Greyish white tissue altogether measuring 0.3cm	Chromogranin and CD56 shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells	Neuroendocrine Tumor Of Duodenum Grade 1
12.	52 yr	Male	? Papillary carcinoma of thyroid	Total thyroidectomy specimen measuring 8x6.5x3.5cm, solid nodule measuring 3x2.5cm present in the left lobe, with calcified areas seen	-	Medullary Thyroid Carcinoma

We found a total of 12 patients diagnosed with neuroendocrine neoplasms involving various organs of the body as shown in Table 1. The mean age of patients was 51.83 years with age varying from 7yrs to 80 yrs. Majority were females with male to female ratio being 7:5. Majority of cases in our setting had involved adrenal glands with three cases diagnosed as pheochromocytoma followed by carotid body tumor (paraganglioma) and medullary carcinoma of thyroid, each with 2 cases respectively and rest all the organs presented with one case each i.e. pituitary, gastric, duodenal, rectum and appendix. Size of the tumors varied from as small as 0.3cm, well defined lesion in duodenum to ill-defined

lesions in adrenals which were diagnosed as pheochromocytoma. After the tissues were sent for histopathological examination, and diagnoses were confirmed, the tissues were sent for immunohistochemistry (IHC). IHC showed strong cytoplasmic positivity for synaptophysin and chromogranin in tumor cells in the cases done. All the cases of neuroendocrine neoplasms diagnosed had rapid mode of presentation with features similar to usual benign lesions of the associated organs, hence it was difficult to diagnose at first in few cases and hence required the assistance of imaging findings.

Figure 1a: HP of Case 1(100x): Microphotograph of pituitary neuroendocrine tumor shows tumor cells arranged in sheets and nests within a fibrovascular stroma

Figure 1b: HP of Case 1 (400x): Individual tumor cells arranged in sheets are small to medium sized, with moderate amounts of amphophilic cytoplasm, centrally placed round nucleus having coarse clumped chromatin and inconspicuous nucleoli

Figure 2a: HP of Case 5(400x): Microphotograph of medullary carcinoma of thyroid shows tumor cells arranged in diffuse sheets surrounded by uniform colloid filled follicles

Figure 2b: HP (400x): Individual tumor cells are round to polygonal cells with round nuclei, fine stippled chromatin and prominent nucleoli, with presence of numerous tumor giant cells

Figure 2c: HP (400x): Microphotograph shows vascular invasion by the tumor cells

Figure 2d: HP (400x): Mitosis seen 3-4/HPF

Figure 3a: HP of Case 6(100x): Microphotograph shows tumor cells arranged in nests (typical zellballen pattern) separated by well demarcated fibrovascular stroma and surrounded by well-defined capsule consistent with paraganglioma

Figure 3b: HP of Case 6 (400x): Individual tumor cells arranged in nests are small to medium sized cells, with moderate amounts of eosinophilic cytoplasm, centrally placed round nucleus having stippled chromatin and conspicuous nucleoli

Figure 4a: HP of Case 8(100x): Microphotograph of Pheochromocytoma shows tumor cells arranged in nests (typical zellballen pattern) separated by well demarcated fibrovascular stroma and surrounded by well-defined capsule

Figure 4b: HP (400x): Individual tumor cells arranged in nests are small to medium sized cells, with moderate amounts of eosinophilic cytoplasm, centrally placed round nucleus having stippled chromatin and conspicuous nucleoli

Figure 4c: IHC (400x): Synaptophysin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells

Figure 4d: IHC (400x): Chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells

Figure 5a: HP of Case 10(100x): Microphotograph shows nested growth of tumor cells in between the normal appendix stroma

Figure 5b: HP (400x): Individual tumor cells are round cells with centrally placed round nucleus having stippled chromatin and conspicuous nucleoli. Mitosis is rare hence consistent with Grade 1 NET of appendix

Figure 5c: IHC (100x): Chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells

Figure 5d: IHC (400x): Ki 67 < 2%

Figure 6a: HP of Case 11(100x): Microphotograph shows tumor cells arranged in sheets and nests within a fibrovascular stroma

Figure 6b: HP (400x): Individual tumor cells arranged in nests are small to medium sized cells, with moderate amounts of eosinophilic cytoplasm, centrally placed round nucleus having salt and pepper chromatin and inconspicuous nucleoli with mitosis < 10/HPF, hence consistent with Grade 2 neuroendocrine tumor of duodenum

Figure 6c: IHC (100x): Chromogranin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells

Figure 6d: IHC (400x): CD56 shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells

Discussion

Neuroendocrine neoplasms (NENs) are rare heterogeneous group of malignancies affecting every organ of our body. They present with a wide variety of histomorphological spectrum and hence become difficult to arrive at the final diagnosis without any aid. The term neuroendocrine means those heterogeneous tumors having both “neuro” and “endocrine” properties [3]. The “neuro” property is based on the fact that they show the presence of dense core granules present in secretory neurons which secrete monoamines. The “endocrine” property is referred to the secretion and synthesis of these monoamines present in the secretory neurons [4]. This explains the concept of functional neuroendocrine tumors secreting biologically active monoamines into the bloodstream [5]. Majority of the neuroendocrine tumors are sporadic with some showing association with familial syndromes like multiple endocrine neoplasia syndromes (MEN1) [6].

Historical perspective shows neuroendocrine neoplasms at the time of discovery by Oberndorfer in 1907 were initially termed as “carcinoids” to refer all those malignancies having less malignant potential. WHO classification of 2000 and 2004 had classified neuroendocrine neoplasms into well differentiated and poorly differentiated types [7]. The WHO 2010 edition further classified NENs into neuroendocrine tumor (NETs) and neuroendocrine carcinomas (NECs). Histopathology is of utmost importance to differentiate these two based on cell proliferation. Histopathologically NETs are characterized by tumor cells arranged in well-developed nests, diffuse sheets, organoid pattern or in trabeculae. The individual tumor cells are small to medium sized cells with uniform round to oval centrally placed nucleus, fine to coarse granular

chromatin typically described as ‘salt and pepper chromatin’ with inconspicuous nucleoli. NECs represent the high grade poorly differentiated type which is characterized by solid proliferation of less defined cells having scant to abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm, nuclear membrane irregularities with nuclear molding having abundant necrosis, apoptotic bodies and high mitotic rates.

The small cell NECs shows hyperchromatic nuclei with typical salt and pepper chromatin. Large cell NECs display vesicular chromatin with conspicuous nucleoli. WHO 2017 edition identified ‘well differentiated NETs as those tumors having well differentiated histomorphology and mitosis > 20/10 HPF, with incorporation of distinguishing NENs based on grading (grade 1-3) and mitotic index. This was done solely for gastro-esophageal-pancreas NENs (GEP NENs). However 2019 edition has defined pancreas NENs to distinguish grade 3 NETs from NECs [8]. The latest 2022 edition of WHO classification of endocrine and neuroendocrine tumors emphasises on the proper classification and grading the tumors based on cell proliferation with further clarification on mixed neuroendocrine and non-neuroendocrine tumors (MiNENs). It also highlights the importance of biomarkers like INSM1, synaptophysin, chromogranin, somatostatin receptors as well as the role of transcription factors [9].

As already mentioned, NETs can affect any organ, Case no. 1 (Figure 1a,b) was a female aged 7 years who presented with non-specific symptoms of increased weight gain, hirsutism and was diagnosed as pituitary neuroendocrine tumor (PitNET). PitNETs are well differentiated neuroendocrine tumors which produce a wide variety of symptoms based on specific hormone production. The term “pituitary adenoma” and “pituitary carcinoma” are

no longer used. PitNETs should be grouped in terms of tumor cell lineage and expression of pituitary hormones by the use of IHC, and whether tumors are derived from a PIT1 lineage (i.e., somatotroph, lactotroph, and thyrotroph), a TPIT lineage (corticotroph tumors), an SF1 lineage (gonadotroph tumors), or tumors without a distinct lineage (plurihormonal lesions and hormonally silent “null cell tumors”), so hormonal study needs to be done [10]. Hormone study like growth hormone (GH), prolactin (PRL), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) for PIT1 tumors; adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) for TPIT tumors; and beta-follicle-stimulating hormone (β -FSH) and beta-luteinizing hormone (β -LH) for SF1 lineage tumors [11]. Keratin IHC like CAM5.2, AE1/AE3, and/or CK18 to subtype somatotroph PitNETs as either densely or sparsely granulated, is also used in some centres.

Case No. 5 (Figure 2a-d) and 12 both elderly individuals presented with thyroid swelling were diagnosed as medullary carcinoma of thyroid (MTC). MTC is derived from the C-cells of thyroid gland which produce calcitonin. 80% cases are sporadic related to RET mutations and rest all are related to multiple endocrine neoplasia syndromes. MTCs can present with different patterns with cell morphology varying from round to plasmacytoid to spindle cells in nests with varying amounts of amyloid deposition in between stroma [12].

Case no. 2 was an elderly female who presented with repeated episodes of diarrhoea, clinically diagnosed as rectal polyp got histopathologically confirmed as rectal carcinoids after IHC. Rectal NETs often diagnosed incidentally may appear as smooth, round yellowish nodules on endoscopy. The tumor metastasis depends on tumor size, endoscopy and histopathological type, since rectal carcinoids are very rare [13]. We had majority cases diagnosed as adrenocortical pheochromocytoma with Case no. 3, 7 and 8 (Figure 4a-d) all seen among elderly age group. Mostly pheochromocytomas are sporadic, with approximately 30% cases hereditary associated with multiple genetic syndromes [14]. Adrenal medullary tumors primarily responsible for secreting epinephrine and is essential to investigate for urinary metanephrines and vanillyl mandelic acid (VMA) assay along with histopathological examination.

Case no.4 clinically thought as gastrointestinal stromal tumor was histopathologically diagnosed as gastric neuroendocrine tumor, grade 2. Gastric NETs account for 7% of all carcinoids constituting 1.8% of all gastric neoplasms. Type 1 gastric NETs found in fundus and body of stomach are often asymptomatic however grade 2 NETs are associated with MEN1, and Zollinger-Ellison syndromes. Type 3 gastric NETs are aggressive and present with poor prognosis [15, 16]. Case no. 11 (Figure 6a, b)

presented with a 0.5x0.5cm over anterior wall of duodenum on endoscopy after nonspecific persistent gastric symptoms for 1 month. With the clinical differential of hyperplastic duodenal polyp, histopathological and IHC confirmed it to be NET grade I. In duodenal NETs, Ki67 is important for the prediction of lymph node metastasis [17].

Usually appendiceal NETs present in females < 50 years age in contrast to our case no. 10 (Figure 5a-d) which is of a 65 yr female. Appendiceal NETs usually have good prognosis and are classified as NET1 or 2 or NEC. Around 60–75% of the tumors are detected at the tip of the appendix [18]. Most appendiceal carcinoids are asymptomatic and are diagnosed post-appendectomy during histopathological examination.

Paraganglioma were diagnosed in Case no.6 (Figure 3a, b) and 9, wherein head and neck paragangliomas are usually parasympathetic non-functioning neuroendocrine tumors. With 40% of the cases associated with gene mutations especially in SDH genes [19]. When paraganglioma presents in locations like the carotid bifurcation or the jugulotympanic area, head and neck paraganglioma is can also be easily diagnosed on histopathological examination.

Diagnosis of all neuroendocrine neoplasms irrespective of organ involved is based on combination of detailed radiological imaging (USG, CT, MRI). Gallium-68-peptide PET/CT is the latest imaging “gold standard” imaging for NETs, biochemical tumor markers specific to the organ involved can also be carried out. However, it is the histopathology with the aid of immunohistochemistry that helps in the confirmation of final diagnosis. Most common IHC markers used in our setting are that of synaptophysin, chromogranin, CD56, NSE and Ki 67 to know the cell proliferation index.

Conclusion

Neuroendocrine neoplasms comprise a highly heterogeneous group of tumors with a wide range of symptoms, making their diagnosis challenging. It is crucial to accurately identify and grade these neoplasms based on histopathological patterns. Immunohistochemistry plays a pivotal role in definitive diagnosis. Therefore, it is important for clinicians, radiologists, and pathologists to consider neuroendocrine neoplasms as a potential diagnosis for any rapidly growing tumor, given their propensity to metastasize.

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